

VERIFICATION OF COMBUSTION AIR TO FCC UNIT REGENERATOR MASS FLOW METERING

Variny M.^{1,2}, Blahušiak M.¹, Mierka O.^{1,2}, Kováč N.³

¹*Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovak republic*

²*GRUCON s.r.o., Nezábudková 24, 821 01 Bratislava, Slovak republic*

³*SLOVNAFT a.s., Vlčie hrdlo 1, 824 12 Bratislava, Slovak republic*
miroslav.variny@stuba.sk

Abstract

This paper deals with the FCC Unit regenerator combustion air mass flow, its verification and its following application in coke burn out rate estimation. The authors, comprising energy auditors that executed the energy audit in SLOVNAFT refinery and the FCC Unit technologist, describe several methodics developed to verify the regenerator combustion air mass flow that are general and thus readily applicable in any FCC Unit worldwide. On having verified it, the calculations based on coke combustion mass balance enabled to estimate the usual coke yield in the range 5 to 6 %, slightly increasing with decreasing feed rate and to obtain hydrogen content in coke. This has been found to vary considerably within 2 to 7 % wt. with no obvious dependence on the feed rate.

Introduction

Reliable and accurate combustion air to regenerator metering in a FCC Unit is an important parameter both from process as well as from economic balance point of view^{1,2}. It is in direct relationship to the mass flow of coke burnt out in the catalyst regenerator that cannot be measured directly, though it can be predicted with known reaction kinetics^{2,3} and is used, along with oxygen and carbon dioxide content in the flue gas⁴, to estimate both this parameter as well as coke quality. It thus serves as an important input parameter in the FCC Unit yield structure estimation⁵, which again is a crucial parameter for long term planning and production scheduling of this Unit, impacting that of the whole refinery. During the energy audit execution in SLOVNAFT refinery, the auditors applied several distinctive approaches to verify this parameter, employing both other measured process data as well as air blower design data and the material balance of the regenerator along with the heat balance of the waste heat boiler. These approaches are introduced and their value in combustion air mass flow metering verification is discussed on following paper pages.

Process scheme

The simplified scheme of FCC Unit regenerator along with key equipment and useful metering devices indication is provided in Figure 1. The combustion air is sucked in the air blower, then passes through the start-up furnace and is delivered to the regenerator. The blower's antisurge control mechanism guards the minimal blower flowrate by blowing off excess air into atmosphere. Additional antisurge protection, applied mostly in winter as antifreeze protection in the same time, allows for manually controlled partial recirculation of compressed air from blower back to its suction. The start-up furnace is in operation only during FCC Unit starts and its aim is to provide sufficient heat for reactor and regenerator proper operation until the coke formation rate rises enough to support the process without combusting natural gas.

During coke burn-out in the regenerator, a small part of the produced flue gas is trapped along with regenerated catalyst and is transported into reactor – evidence of such process is obtained from C2 fraction analysis which shows appr. 20 % vol. nitrogen content along with a few % of carbon dioxide and traces of oxygen. This issue has been consulted repeatedly with the responsible technologist but no other feasible explanation of the observed C2 fraction composition could be provided. At the same time a part of the stripping water steam used in the reactor is transported with the spent catalyst and joins the flue gas, whereby its moisture content is increased. This has been repeatedly found in the results of regular emission monitoring executed by a certified company; the measured moisture content of the flue gas of up to 12 % vol. cannot be explained by any other means despite taking combustion air humidity and reasonable hydrogen content in the burnt-out coke into account. Both fuel gas entrainment to reactor and water steam entrainment into regenerator have to be considered when balancing the coke burn-out process.

Hot flue gases from regenerator pass through orifice chamber where their overpressure is decreased from around 2 bar to a few kPa and are routed to the waste heat steam boiler. Saturated water steam is produced from the feedwater here, thereafter it joins the saturated steam from other steam sources, is superheated in common superheater and leaves the boiler at around 3.5 MPa (g) and 340 °C. The partly cooled down flue

gases pass through an electrostatic precipitator and finally enter into the stack. Their composition on dry basis is monitored by several analyzers, including those for oxygen and carbon dioxide content measurement.

Figure 1. Simplified process layout

Underlying data and their analysis

Based on the discussion with Unit's staff and their own experience the auditors decided to employ following approaches to obtain the combustion air mass flow

1. Comparison of blower inlet air measurement with catalyst regenerator air inlet measurement
2. Material balance of the regenerator and the following heat balance of the waste heat boiler
3. Analysis of blower characteristics and its application to blower air delivery rate estimation
4. Field experiment with air preheat furnace during FCC Unit start phase after a short production stop

Reasons for choosing several distinctive approaches to air mass flow measurement verification and the extra effort the auditors took in it were as follows:

- Air mass flow measured at blower suction exhibited too low values compared to the air to the regenerator measurement, even lower than the compressor antisurge control would allow. Air mass flow verification would greatly help the auditors in checking if the blower antisurge protection does operate with reasonable margin or if it could be narrowed.
- Flue gas volumetric flow measurement was also suspected of incorrect metering, leading to under- or overestimation of emission rates from the regenerator.
- Waste heat steam boiler heat balance served also as confirmation for Unit's steam balance.
- Air blower is driven by condensing steam turbine, proper air mass flow estimation compressed by the blower would allow for blower power input calculation and thus for its turbine steam consumption verification.
- Coke burn out rate could be estimated more precisely; this would greatly help the auditors in the reactor-regenerator heat balance setup and in the end it would contribute to precisising the FCC Unit mass balance and its yield structure

More information regarding the approaches 1. to 4. is as follows:

- 1.: The auditors checked the equations and their constants used in air mass flow measurement. It has been found out that the blower inlet air mass flows shown on the operator's screen in the control room has not been compensated on actual air pressure and temperature. Instead, 95 kPa abs. and +34 °C were used. The auditors subsequently were able to compensate the raw data to actual air parameters.
- 2.: Considering the typical C2 fraction composition and its yield, it has been calculated that around 800 to 1100 kg/h of flue gas is entrained into reactor, depending on actual operating conditions, especially on catalyst circulation rate. On the other hand, up to 1500 kg/h of water steam seem to pass together with spent catalyst into regenerator. Both these effects have been incorporated into flue gas composition and mass flow calculation and enabled more precise waste heat steam boiler heat balance elaboration.
- 3.: Blower characteristics represents the map of allowed combinations of compressed air volumetric flows and discharge pressures, depending on blower rotation frequency and on inlet air parameters. It also comprises borders corresponding to expected surge and choke conditions as well as another border denoting the minimal air volumetric flows to be compressed by the blower that is maintained by blower's antisurge protection automatics. Given the measured pressure at blower inlet is the same as design one the auditors were able to interpolate between the compressors maps valid for -29 °C and +34 °C ambient temperature, with the aim to estimate compressed air volumetric flow based on actual air temperature, blower discharge pressure and its actual revolutions per minute.
- 4.: The FCC Unit is equipped with a start up furnace, combusting natural gas directly in the compressed air flowing through it. Given the known natural gas composition, by combining the material and heat balance of its combustion it has been possible to calculate the air mass flow that entered the furnace.

Field experiment description and acquired data evaluation

After a short production stop the FCC Unit started its operation according to its usual schedule. Due to the lack of coke formed in the reactor, natural gas fired furnace has been used for several hours to preheat the air prior entering the regenerator, firing enough natural gas to raise the air temperature up to 700 °C. Despite this, the comparatively low air consumption in the regenerator made it necessary, to operate the air blow off at the blower discharge, to ensure safe, surge free blower operation during this phase.

Data needed for natural gas consumption process balancing included:

- Mass flow of natural gas (directly measured on site by coriolis flowmeter and thus assumed to be accurate),
- its average composition (acquired from the national natural gas distributor's web site) and
- temperatures of the air at blower discharge and at furnace discharge (both measured on site, see Figure 1).

Due to small surface and the fact that the furnace and air duct are well insulated, zero heat losses to the environment were assumed.

Apart from those data, we also acquired other operational data including ambient air temperature, blower operation, opening percentage of the blow off valve as well as flue gas composition, that ex post enabled for simultaneous application of several air mass flow rate verification approaches described above.

Results and discussion

The overall look on the test duration and the outcome of the following calculations is provided in Figure 2. Around 5 a.m. the start up furnace reached stable operation represented by stable mass flow of natural gas consumed here. During this phase, starting at 5 a.m. and ending at around 0:30 p.m. the temperature in the furnace varied in the range 710 to 725 °C, starting to decrease after midday, leading to the conclusion that in this phase also the air mass flow to the furnace has been quite stable.

With the help of compressor characteristics (operation maps) valid for two distinctive design air temperatures we were able to calculate the position of „control line“ (dataset Nr. 5 in the Figure 2) for actual blower inlet air temperatures – the „control line“ represents the border conditions for blower operation without antisurge control system taking charge of blow off valve opening percentage regulation. In order to prevent the antisurge system to act and thereby inevitably interrupt the test, the operators adjusted the needed blow off valve opening manually. Therefore we could expect the true air mass flow rate compressed in the blower to be higher than that indicated by „control line“.

Heat balance of the start up furnace yielded dataset Nr. 1 that adopted quite similar values with on line measured air mass flow to the furnace (and thus to the regenerator) shown as dataset Nr. 2. This represents the first proof of air to regenerator flow rate metering accuracy.

Dataset Nr. 4 represents the on line measured air mass flow rate at blower suction that again yielded lower values than the „control line“. If those data were correct, blower surge occurrence probability would be high

due to antisurge system failure to increase the compressed air mass flow above the control line. However as explained above, the original data from this flowmeter suffer under the absence of compensation on actual air pressure and temperature at blower suction. After having executed the compensation, we yielded the dataset Nr. 6 that is positioned slightly above the „control line“ and may thus represent reasonable air mass flow at blower suction data.

Figure 2. Overview of calculated air mass flows and measured temperature at the start up furnace discharge during the test.

Legend: 1: Air mass flow to the start up furnace calculated from its heat balance, 2: Measured air mass flow rate to regenerator (metering element located prior to start up furnace), 3: NG to the start up furnace flow rate, 4: Measured air mass flow rate at blower suction – original data, 5: „control line“ air mass flow denoting the minimal air mass flow to be compressed in the blower to ensure its surge free operation, 6: Measured air mass flow rate at blower suction – compensated data, 7: Sum of 1 and the air mass flow through the blow off valve, 8: air mass flow rate compressed in blower according to its characteristics

With the help of on line recorded blow off valve opening percentage and its design parameters (capacity at given pressure differential and inlet air temperature), assuming linear dependence of unit blow off capacity on valve opening percentage we obtained an estimate of air mass flow rate blown off in the atmosphere during the test. Adding these data to the dataset Nr. 1 we got dataset Nr. 7 that should represent the total air mass flow compressed by the blower. As appears, the corresponding values are higher than those of dataset Nr. 6. Finally, employing once again the compressor characteristics and using the on line recorded data about the blower inler air temperature and pressure, blower discharge pressure and blower revolutions per minute, we calculated the compressed air mass flow. The corresponding data set is marked with Nr. 8 in the Figure 2. As appears it agrees with dataset Nr.7 excellently, thus corroborating both the air mass flow rate obtained from furnace’s heat balance as well as sufficient air to regenerator metering accuracy.

We can therefore conclude, that the air to regenerator measurement is correct and can be used for coke burn out rate calculation.

Having verified the air to regenerator mass flow, we proceeded with coke burn out rate calculation and its quality estimation. Following assumptions have been made:

- coke consists just from carbon and hydrogen
- entrained flue gas to reactor mass flow is constant, equal to 700 kg/h
- oxygen and carbon dioxide analyzers of the flue gas yield reliable data – such assumption is crucial for our calculation as even small variations in those parameters can influence the result significantly^{4,5}.

Figure 3. Results of coke yield and composition calculations

Applying these assumptions on historic operational data set, comprising the 2009 to 2010 period, we finally obtained the desired data that are shown in Figure 3 as functions of relative FCC Unit feed rate. It appears that the coke yield rises slightly with decreasing feed rate which probably is not surprising⁵. The heat delivery demand to reactor that is covered by coke burn out covers also some fix part (recycles independent on actual feed rate) plus also heat losses from reactor, thus the coke yield has to be controlled as to cope with this fact. The second finding relates to hydrogen weight fraction in coke that seems to vary mostly within 2 to 7 % that is slightly below average of the common coke hydrogen content reported in the literature^{1,4,5}. It does not seem to change visibly with changing feed.

It can thus be stated that the FCC reactor produces coke with acceptable hydrogen content and the coke yield is managed according to the heat demands of the reactor.

Conclusions

A part of the energy audit of the FCC Unit in SLOVNAFT refinery has been dedicated to regenerator combustion air measurement verification, a key parameter impacting the operation and economics of the unit and also that of the whole refinery to some extent. Various approaches based on discussion with the Unit's staff and its technologist have been developed and tested, leading to final statement about the regenerator air mass flow measurement accuracy being acceptable. The presented approaches are general in nature and can be used, after adjustment to local FCC Unit's specificities in any refinery worldwide. The following coke burn out rate calculations revealed that coke yield in the FCC Unit understudy varies within 5 to 6 % interval, slightly increasing with decreasing feed. The simultaneously estimated hydrogen content in the coke varies considerably but on the whole is slightly below average and might lead to flue gas analyzers accuracy questioning.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express their gratitude towards the SLOVNAFT refinery FCC Unit staff and former Chief Technologists Department members for their support during energy audit execution and also afterwards in the energy saving measures implementation phase. They contributed much also to the content of the presented paper.

References

1. Wolschlag L. M., Couch K. A., Zhu F., Alves J.: UOP FCC DESIGN ADVANCEMENTS TO REDUCE ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND CO₂ EMISSIONS, p. 1. Available online at: <http://www.uop.com/?document=uop-fcc-energy-optimization-tech-paper&download=1>. Accessed on 05.04.2016.
2. Lee L-S., Chen Y-W., Huang T-N.: *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* **4**, 615 (2009).
3. Rajeev N., Prasad R. K., Ragula U. B. R.: *Pet. Sci. Technol.* **1**, 111 (2015).
4. Marri R. R., Soni D.: Catalyst stripper improves FCC unit performance, p. 1. Available online at: http://www.cbi.com/images/uploads/technical_articles/Catalyst_Stripper_improves_FCC_unit_performance_-_PTQ_3Q12.pdf. Accessed on 11.04.2016.
5. Dasila P K., Choudhury I., Saraf D., Chopra S., Dalai A.: *Adv. Chem. Eng. Sci.*, **2**, 132 (2012).